

Portrayal of Post Colonial Santal Society by a Subaltern Tribal Writer in English

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Abstract: *Santals are one of the most ancient indigenous communities in our country. Their culture and tradition are still glowing in the era of post-modern world. This paper discusses about the position of women in Santal Society through the eyes of the characters depicted by Hansda Sowvendra Sekhar in his well-read books 'The Mysterious Ailment of Rupy Baskey' and 'My Father's Garden'. Here we find the multiple layers of discrimination and marginality also prevailed among the villagers. Polygamy among the characters shows the suppression of women. "Amongst Santals women bodies are not considered appropriate vessels to receive gods. Naturalistic idea of Emily Zola is vividly applied. Emancipation of British raj made them joyous with the hope of making utopian society. Migration is common to the society. Post Colonial resistance in the women characters has also been seen. The legacy of Santali culture and tradition has snugly inscribed in his writings. Again in 'My Father's Garden', Homosexuality, Exploitation, Emotional Intensiveness etc are the main themes.*

Keywords: *Discrimination, Polygamy, Naturalism, Post Colonial resistance, Exploitation, Migration.*

INTRODUCTION: Santar or Santals are one of the largest tribes among Austroasiatic Munda ethnic group. They are found not only in the states of Jharkhand rather in the states of West Bengal, Bihar, Assam and Tripura also. Their unique identity is still glowing even in Twenty First century. Their language, art, dance music everything has its own rationality. The song plays pivotal role in their lives. Songs are not only emancipating our lethargy better to say every song has own special meaning and has its own purpose. Swovendra Sekhar marked this unique tribal identity by using songs in his novel 'Mysterious Ailment of Rupy Baskey'. Again, the narrator's obsession with sexuality in 'His Father's Garden' shows the resistance of stereotypes nuisance. This blending of identity and resistance is unanimously depicted in his two novels.

The Mysterious Ailment of Rupy Basley: The mysterious ailment of Rupy Basley depicts the village life and its people good and evil-who influence them. The story evolves round the Basley family -the patriarch Somai, his alcoholic daughter Putki, Khorda, Putki's devoted husband and their sons Sido and Doso; Sido's wife Rupi. The various small and large dramas of the Baskeys' lives play out. The village cheers them on and 'enjoys' the spectacle they provide.

Social Identity in Different Songs:

1. The Song of Marriage: Every song has different names in Santal Society. The song 'Dong' has mostly been sung during the occasion of marriage. The song-
"Aleya bargey rey ma kocha bargey rey ma/Kadam mulin baha poroi-poroi"

"In our garden, our corner garden/Look!the kadam flowers have blossomed."

Sung by Putki. It shows an auspicious marriage has done among Rupi with Sido and Gurubari with Bairam in the village Kadamdihi, Tereldihi. The name of villages after the names of trees show the tribals' deep affection towards nature.

2. The Song of Apparitions: The apparitions, Dhonkundra-Bhoot (a small child-or a dwarf, no taller than three feet -with large, saucer-like eyes and a small, pinched mouth) is singing:

“Noawa do aleya bandi/ Nowa ho aleya bandi /Nowa doo Kaalay-ak baandi”
“This is our Gola/This too is our Gola/This one is Kalaya’s Gola”

Bandi means where Paddies are being kept. This song of apparition indicates some mischief is going to happen in the house of Samai Haram. Eventually Somai Budhi was miscarriage even after her mother’s outstanding efforts. It reminds us the unnatural incident in Macbeth, when three witches are singing – “Fair is foul and foul is fair/Hover through the fog and filthy air”

3.Hahal: Hahal (Encouragement) plays vital role in Santali Traditional Songs. It encourages the dancers as well as the drummer to sing more enthusiastically. It makes the atmosphere more pleasant. It’s unique identity of Santali song which has not been found any other songs. Here the village youngsters chanting:

“Haram kada- y thali a-kan
Gidhi malai – malai
Kiya baha mohey a- kan
Kora malay – malay”

Meaning: “The old Buffalo is caught in the more/Greedy vultures eyed him, their mouths water/The young woman has bloomed like the fragrant kiya flower/ Young man lust after her, their mouths water”

It echoes “The Sick Rose” by William Blake- “O Rose thou art sick /The invisible worm/That flies in the night /In the howling storm” — Invisible worm like young men are wandering to seduce kiya flower like young woman.

4.The Song of the Post Colonial Resistance:

Ho, Santhal, Mahaley -Munda.
Abo jhoto bowak runda”

Meaning:Ho Santhal Mahaley and Munda /we all purr together, like the civet.

Dela and Putki heard this anthem on the roads, the song which would unite the chief Adivasi communities of the region. After the long Colonial period, it had been spread in the air that now the Sarkar or Government would be run by own people. Tribals like Ho, Santhal, Mahaley, Munda also demanded separate land for them. Its a satirical song to resist against coloniser. The then Tribal leader Jaipal Sing Munda from Ranchi had led Adivasis after Independence. He founded Adivasi Mahasava later renamed as Jharkhand Party and he demanded that the reservation should be granted to Adivasi all over India. To them freedom is like “The utopian Government which the Adivasis of the Chota Nagpur region had been striving for so long seemed within reach ,like a ripe guava hanging from the lower most branch of a tree, brought down low by its own weight”.

5.The Song of Exploitation:

Hai-re hai- re hai-re
Devi ar Durga do kin udugena re
Devi ar Durga do kin baherena re
Cheda do kin udugena re
Hai-re Hai-re Hai -re Hai

Meaning: Devi and Durga have left their houses/Devi and Durga have come out of their houses /Why have they left their houses? Sung by Khorda.

It’s a Dasai song, sung during the time of ‘Durgoutsav’. It has been a belief that two young and beautiful ladies Ainom and Kajol has been molested and exploited by some other casts. So Devi and Durga were lamenting and coming out from their houses in search of them. The males dance in disguise of a women so that none can recognise them.

Discrimination: “There will be outcast as long as there are castes. Nothing can emancipate the outcaste except the destruction of the caste system” by B R Ambedkar.

In the village Kadamdih among the santals there arrived two other communities, these are Kamar, the blacksmith and Kunal, the potter. Though their rank was lower in Hindi religion but they strongly believed that “The shadow of a Santhal was enough to defile them”. But the villagers of Kadamdih did not tolerate so long. They raised their voice against such discrimination. Khorda Haram, Head of the village raised his voice and declared “Listen all of you. All of you who are not saotal we stand against you and revolt against you”

The Mystery of Rupy Baskey’s Ailment: After being sick many treatments went on for Rupi including medical treatment and alternative therapies. But nothing cured her. People asked her to take her to Ojha. But Ojha also did not do anything as witchcraft prevailed in their family. About the mysteries of their family. People of Kadamdih rightly said “The immortality of Putki’s youth has come back to haunt her. Rupi’s disease isn’t hers alone. It is Putki’s, it is Sido’s, Doso’s and Dulari’s”.

My Father’s Garden

Hansda Sowvendra Sekhar’s novel ‘My Father’s Garden’ deals with the narrator’s obsession with Homosexuality, Political ambition, racial conflict and environmental issues. The saga is depicted in First Person narration who is a medical student and divided into three sections.

Narrator’s Obsession: The opening section begins “Men are hard to and he was one to die for” shows his too much obsession with sexuality. The narrator’s homosexual relationships with Samir broke the stereotype notions of society.

Discrimination And His Father’s Garden: The third chapter depicted his relationship with his father. They are from the remote area of the southern part of Jharkhand. His father was the son of Dadu who had several children. As his grandfather was the MAJHE of the village, so the peace and prosperity of the village was on his hand. Discrimination was so much prevailed in the society – “Santals were looked down upon by the members of the higher castes and classes as uncivilized people and given all kinds of insulting and humiliating names”. Sometimes they had resisted but most of the time the cases remain background.

The intercaste marriage is prohibited in Indian traditional society. As Chetan Bhagat has narrated about intercaste marriage in his ‘The Story of Marriage’, “Love marriage around world is simple. Boy loves girl, girl loves boy. The girl’s family has to love the boy and the boy’s family has to love a girl. The girl’s family has to love boy’s family. The boy’s family has to love girl’s family. Girl and boy still love each other. Then they get married”. The similar incident a Santhal girl had relationship with a Bihari boy and fell pregnant by him. But when the boy was asked to marry her, he refused. The boy’s family remarked “Why would they bring an untouchable girl home as their daughter in law? The political ambition of his father led their family better position in the society. But the casteism within the Party, did not allow him to do much more to his own people. His father was very much obsessed with his garden. After his retirement from politics the trees around their house and its soothing breeze gives him immense peace. The naturalistic idea of Emily Zola that “the things happening in the world are not a result of spiritual Will, but are a necessity of nature”. His father wanders if the obsession of choices in the garden has ever made then his son has made.

Conclusion: The post-colonial cultural identity in ‘The Mysterious Ailment of Rupy Baskey ’is vividly ascribed. Their unique songs, paintings, dancing etc revokes the Traditionalism of Indian Society. The Women’s resistance against patriarchy unveils the new hope in the society. The political leadership makes the changes of their destiny. Again in ‘His Father’s Garden’, echoed the voice of Subaltern writer. The detailed descriptions of everything shows that the narrator has raised his Subaltern voice in the field of ‘Mainstream’ English Literature. The amalgamation of traditionality and Post Modernity make the readers think highly of the Santal Society.

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